

Annual Report

2019 – 2020

1 Preamble	2
2 The Structure of ODISSEI	3
3 Activities	5
3.1 The Data Facility	5
3.1.1 Statistics Netherlands Microdata Access	5
3.1.2 ODISSEI Data Products	6
3.1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer	6
3.1.4 ODISSEI Portal	7
3.2 The Observatory	9
3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee	9
3.1.2 Historical Sample of the Netherlands	9
3.1.3 National Twin Registry	9
3.2.4 Media Content Analysis Lab	9
3.3 The Laboratory	11
3.3.1 Distributed Analytics	11
3.3.2 Automated Data Linkage	11
3.3.3 The LISS Panel	11
3.4 The Hub	13
3.4.1 Community Management	13
3.4.2 Educational Programme	13
3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Analytics Team	13
3.4.4 Computational Social Science Grants	14
3.4.5 Benchmarking	14
4 Governance	15
5 Financial Results 2019-2020	16
6 Plans for 2020-2024	18
Annex 1 – Microdata Access Discount	19

1 Preamble

The year 2019-2020 has been a landmark year in ODISSEI's development. Our roadmap proposal was successful, and whilst we will need to seek further funding to realise our full ambitions, the investment we have received from NWO and our member organisations is allowing us to develop a ground-breaking and truly innovative national infrastructure for social science.

This year has demonstrated the need for such an infrastructure like no other. The onset of the pandemic unleashed a wave of scientific research and a huge increase in demand for high quality data in a short time period. We were exceptionally proud to be able to offer researchers the opportunity to field COVID-19-related questions within the Longitudinal Internet Study for Social Sciences (LISS) panel during the lockdown in April. The period from conceiving the call to researchers having data in hand was just 6 weeks, which is a remarkable demonstration of the capacity and potential of the LISS panel and its team. Furthermore, we were able to assist the large-scale data collections (e.g. Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), the Dutch Election Study (NKO), the Generations and Gender Survey (GGS) and the European Social Survey (ESS)) in adapting to exceptionally demanding fieldwork circumstances and to meet the challenges we are now facing.

The pandemic has underlined the vital role of scientific data in understanding the world around us. Within weeks of the outbreak in Wuhan, biomedical infrastructures had made the virus's genetic sequencing publicly available, aiding in the rapid development of more efficient testing, more effective treatments and hopefully to the eventual development of a vaccine. Social data infrastructures have been less effective. In the next few years, ODISSEI should be able to provide more secure and more immediate access to the data that matter, when they matter. To meet this challenge, we will not only be implementing our own Roadmap proposal, but also working closely with researchers in the health sciences, environmental sciences and the humanities to ensure that the social component is never lacking in the understanding of daily lives.

This year has also been challenging given that one of ODISSEI's primary aims is to develop a computational social science community in the Netherlands and foster its growth. Doing that without face to face meetings, social events, workshops, and summer schools is asking for new routines from all of us. We will have to rethink and reinvent what we understand by community and the ways in which we can support researchers looking to engage with computational social science. These are exceptional times and exceptional challenges but ones that ODISSEI can rise to as we seek to implement an exciting and impactful program of work.

Pearl Dykstra
Scientific director, ODISSEI

2 The Structure of ODISSEI

The ODISSEI acronym stands for Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations. At present, ODISSEI is made up of 40 [member organisations](#) that financially contribute to its development. These member organisations include Social Science Faculties, Economics Faculties, Research Institutes, Public Research Agencies, Statistics Netherlands, and E-Infrastructure providers. The 40 member organisations in ODISSEI represent more than 5,000 social science researchers and ODISSEI aims to support their research by providing world class data infrastructure services that increase their access to data, computing tools, expertise and financial resources.

The [Supervisory Board](#) is elected by the member organisations to represent their interests and oversee the development of ODISSEI. In turn the Supervisory Board appoints the [Management Board](#) of ODISSEI with overseeing ODISSEI's programme of work. This programme of work was set out in the ODISSEI Roadmap application which has a budget of € 13.9 million and runs through to 2024. The implementation of the work programme is the responsibility of 13 service providers, all of whom are ODISSEI member organisations. These 13 providers are coordinated by the [Coordination Team](#) at Erasmus University Rotterdam as the host participant of ODISSEI.

The programme of work is sub-divided into four work streams which represent four separate ways in which ODISSEI serves the research community. First, the **Data Facility** ensures that researchers can find, access, and link the data that they need through Microdata Access Grants and the Microdata Access Discount. To enhance the analytical experience once researchers have access, the Data Facility has developed the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer which allows researchers to analyse complex and rich data from Statistics Netherlands and other ODISSEI data providers in a secure, yet computationally powerful environment.

The **Observatory** supports and maintains key long-standing data collection efforts and participation in the international social science data collections to which the Ministry of Education and Culture has committed itself (via so-called ERICs, European Research Infrastructure Consortiums). These include such studies as the European Social Survey, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe and the Generations and Gender Programme. It also covers the Dutch Election Study which has been collecting data since 1971. This work stream is focused on providing a consistent, stable, and reliable stream of data for social scientists that could then be utilised across the infrastructure.

The **Laboratory** is where researchers can conduct their own experiments, primarily through the LISS Panel, operated by CentERdata. ODISSEI provides financing for the core LISS Panel but also provides access to researchers from ODISSEI member organisations to field their own questions to the LISS panel's representative and high-quality sample of over 4,500 households. The Laboratory is also where future ODISSEI upgrades and enhancements are developed and prototyped.

Finally, the **Hub** is where researchers are provided with support, expertise, and guidance in the use of ODISSEI services and facilities. It includes an educational programme, community events, remote access

grants, data stewardship, as well a social data analytics team at Utrecht University who can provide high quality and intensive support to researchers looking to deploy computational and data science methods within ODISSEI.

As a community, ODISSEI not only delivers services but also develops and promotes standards and best practices for social science research. For example, ODISSEI not only promotes the **FAIR principles**¹ through the delivery of new search and access services, but also by requiring adherence to FAIR from ODISSEI users. ODISSEI requires its users to act in accordance with the **principles of responsible data science**: Fair, Accurate, Confidential and Transparent (FACT)². ODISSEI also supports open science by facilitating inclusion, sharing, and equity through its work. These principles are set out in the ODISSEI terms of participation which will be approved by the Management Board by the end of 2020 and launched in early 2021.

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://redasci.org/>

3 Activities

In 2019-2020, ODISSEI conducted activities in four work streams as defined in the ODISSEI Roadmap proposal: The Data Facility, the Observatory, the Laboratory, and the Hub. This section details those activities and the work that has been conducted at the time of reporting.

3.1 The Data Facility

3.1.1 Statistics Netherlands Microdata Access

ODISSEI stimulates the use of the rich microdata at Statistics Netherlands. These microdata are (pseudonymised) available at the level of individuals, companies, and addresses. The data can be made available to researchers in the secured Statistics Netherlands environment under strict conditions for statistical research³, and combined with researchers' own datasets. However, the costs for obtaining access to these data can be prohibitive, especially for early-career researchers.

In early 2020, ODISSEI launched its annual call to facilitate access to microdata from Statistics Netherlands free or charge for researchers at ODISSEI member organisations (so-called **Microdata Access Grants**, MAG). The submission deadline was 30 April 2020. There were 16 applications to this call, which is a decline from the 24 received the year before. This is likely due to the impact of Corona on application preparations and the inability to host an engagement event. Two submissions were not eligible because they were from a non-member organisation or were a project using the Microdata Access Discount (MAD). In June, eight projects of ODISSEI member organisations were awarded an ODISSEI Microdata Access Grant (Table 1). The total value of the awarded projects is **€ 40,211** (see the far-right column of Table 3 on page 17).

The proposals were assessed by an independent, interdisciplinary committee consisting of Tanja van der Lippe (Utrecht University), Didier Fouarge (Maastricht University), Jan van Ours (Erasmus University Rotterdam), Maarten van Ham (TU Delft), and Govert Bijwaard (NIDI). Committee members were excluded from evaluating proposals with which they expressed to have some kind of connection. Each proposal was evaluated by three committee members. The committee then approved the final ranking of proposals.

ODISSEI also continued the **Microdata Access Discount** (MAD) in collaboration with Statistics Netherlands. From July 2019 to June 2020, ODISSEI provided a discount of up to 50% to 143 Statistics Netherlands microdata projects from ODISSEI member organisations. The total value of these discounts was **€ 256,716**. A full list of projects to have received the discount is available in Annex 1. Member organisations are however prohibited from claiming more than double their annual contributions.

³ <https://www.cbs.nl/en-gb/our-services/customised-services-microdata/microdata-conducting-your-own-research>

Table 1 - Microdata Access Grant Awardees 2020

Applicant	Affiliation	Project Title
Joost Oude Groeniger	EUR-ESSB	Do neighbourhoods affect health? Disentangling selection and causation
Gijs Custers	EUR-ESSB	Breaking the barrier? The effects of the National Program Rotterdam South on educational mobility
Elanie Rodermond	NSCR	From inside prison to a prison outside: Re-integration and recidivism during the corona-crisis
Daniel Karpati	TiSEM	Does the lack of collateral prevent the creation and growth of small businesses?
Massimo Giuliadori	UvA-FEB	The 30%-rule for expats: impact on immigration and wages
Koen Kuijpers	UT-BMS	The influence of regional logics in altering organizational behaviour in decentralized states
Giuseppe Floccari	TiSEM	Systematic income risk
Jennifer Holland	EUR-ESSB	New work and the family life course in the Netherlands (NeWFam-NL)

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.2 ODISSEI Data Products

In 2020, on the back of the successful ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer pilot, the Coordination Team decided to cultivate a range of data products that would be available for reuse within the Statistics Netherlands remote access environment and in the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer. During the pilot, several projects produced results that could form the basis of further results including (a) geo-spatial maps of the Netherlands which would provide rich contextual information to individual records and (b) network files which would represent pseudonymised individuals as embedded within their networks. Since August 2020 Statistics Netherlands and the ODISSEI Coordination Team have been working on the development and documentation of a whole population network file that will be available to authorised users within the Statistics Netherlands secure remote access environment. Further data products will be added to the environment in early 2021.

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Statistics Netherlands and SURF delivered a fully operational version of the **ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer** (OSSC) in September 2020. The ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer provides the fastest computing capacity in the Netherlands via the national supercomputer and obeys the highest standards for data protection both legally and technically, imposed by both Statistics Netherlands Law and Europe's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It provides Statistics Netherlands' secure remote-access environment that can incorporate datasets and advanced analytics tools at the national supercomputer of SURF. Datasets include pseudonymised administrative microdata on persons, households, companies etc. from Statistics Netherlands as well as research data collected by ODISSEI members. Analysis of these highly secured datasets is possible due to the system's architecture: SURF

acts as Trusted Third Party between the data provider and the researcher, and the analysis environment is strictly **controlled and protected**. In August 2020, the OSSC illustrated its security by passing a second penetration test performed by the digital security company Secura⁴.

Development of the OSSC cost € 96,340 in 2019-2020 which was exclusively for SURF (see the far-right column of Table 3). This included the costs of a penetration test and adaptations to ensure the OSSC can service all member organisations. The OSSC was formally launched in October 2020 and is now working with 13 researchers who have expressed an interest in using the facility. Interest in the OSSC has been overwhelming and comes from a wide variety of member organisations, as well as from organisations that are not yet a member of ODISSEI (e.g. Centre for Mathematics and Computer Science (CWI) and LUMC). Through 2021 these projects will be supported in their implementation and usage of OSSC with the Coordination Team monitoring progress.

Table 2 - Expression of Interest list for use of the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer

Researcher	Affiliation
Elenna Dugundji	Centrum Wiskunde & Informatica (CWI)
Eva-Maria Merz	Vrije Universiteit (VU) - Faculteit der Sociale Wetenschappen
Alexandros Dimitropoulos	Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving (PBL)
Ana Petrović	TU Delft (TUD) - Faculty Architecture and the Built Environment
Maciek Strak	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM)
Mikhail Sirenko	TU Delft (TUD) - Faculty Architecture and the Built Environment
Jasper Selder	Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS)
Daniel Oberski	Universiteit Utrecht (UU) - Faculteit der Sociale Wetenschappen
Leo Huberts	Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) - Faculteit Economie en Bedrijfskunde
Brechtje de Mooij	Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA) - Faculteit der Maatschappij en Gedragwetenschappen
Eric Schaap	Universiteit Maastricht (UM) - School of Business and Economics
Bastian Ravesteijn	Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (EUR) - Erasmus School of Economics
Jeniffer Holland	Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (EUR) - School of Social and Behavioural Sciences

Coordination Team Contact: Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.4 ODISSEI Portal

The **ODISSEI Portal** promotes the reuse of existing datasets by making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). Reusing existing datasets, rather than creating new ones, can result in lower costs (because data collection is not needed), a better data quality (because professional panels

⁴ www.secura.com/penetration-testing

or register data carefully curate their data) and richer data (because professional panels and register data are inherently rich). By combining and linking datasets, new research questions can be addressed.

To facilitate FAIR use of data, the portal will provide a variable level, searchable catalogue of data within ODISSEI member organisations. In 2020, the Portal working group was established and consists of representatives from DANS, VU, SURF and the ODISSEI Coordination team. The budget for this work in 2019-2020 was **€ 82,925** which allowed for the continuation of project staff at SURF. Under this working group, the preliminary design and development of the Portal has begun with bi-weekly meetings and consultation with initial key strategic data providers at Statistics Netherlands and CentERdata. The aim is to develop a first iteration of the Portal in which administrative data at Statistics Netherlands and panel data from LISS are searchable through the same portal. This will help researchers who are applying to use LISS or Statistics Netherlands microdata through ODISSEI grants and access discounts in navigating the pre-existing data collections and rapidly identifying possible linkages and synergies between the data sources. In later years of the project, further data sources will be added to extend the coverage and functionality of the Portal.

Coordination Team Contact: Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

3.2 The Observatory

3.2.1 ODISSEI Data Collection Committee

ODISSEI finances Dutch participation in ERIC surveys and surveys of key strategic importance. For example, ODISSEI is responsible for financing the Netherlands Election Study (NKO), the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) and **European Social Survey (ESS - € 45,000)**. ODISSEI also paid the Dutch contribution for 2019 of the Luxembourg Income Study (**LIS - € 36,300**).

To ensure that all fieldwork efforts within ODISSEI are efficient and that the resulting data can be fully integrated within ODISSEI, a new **Data Collection Committee** of four members has been appointed: Marike Knoef (Chair), Gerbert Kraaykamp, Ineke Stoop, and Bella Struminskaya. Tom Emery acts as the Coordination Team support for the committee. In 2021 the committee will be overseeing the implementation of the European Social Survey, the Dutch Election Study, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe, and the Generations and Gender Survey. This coordination has become increasingly important given the impact of the COVID pandemic on fieldwork operations.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.2 Historical Sample of the Netherlands

The program of work for the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN) is currently being finalised and will focus on linking the historical data file with the population registers held by Statistics Netherlands. Actual work is expected to start in early 2021 and will form a key bridge to the work conducted in CLARIAH.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.1.3 National Twin Registry

The program of work for the National Twin Register (NTR) is currently being finalised and will focus on linking biomedical and cognitive data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof of concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating the diverse metadata of NTR in the ODISSEI Portal. Actual work is expected to start in early 2021 and will form a key bridge to the work conducted in Consortium on Individual Development (CID)⁵ and BBMRI (Netherlands Biobank Research Facility)⁶.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.2.4 Media Content Analysis Lab

The program of work for the Media Content Analysis Lab (MCAL) is currently being finalised and will focus on linking social media and textual media data with the wider ODISSEI infrastructure through proof of concept projects within the ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer and integrating the diverse

⁵ <https://individualdevelopment.nl/>

⁶ <https://www.bbmri.nl/>

metadata of MCAL in the ODISSEI Portal. The MCAL will also be exploring ways in which media data on coverage of the 2021 Dutch parliamentary elections can be linked to and compliment the data collected by the Dutch Election Study (NKO). Actual work is expected to start in early 2021 and will form a key bridge to the work conducted in communication sciences.

Coordination Team Contact: Tom Emery (tom@odissei-data.nl)

3.3 The Laboratory

3.3.1 Distributed Analytics

The program of work for Distributed Analytics is currently under development. A primary use case involving the analysis of primary school students with special educational needs has been identified and is being developed in collaboration with Rolf van der Velden (Maastricht University). The distributed analytics system which has been developed by Michel Dumontier (also at Maastricht University) will allow researchers to run analysis on highly sensitive data without having access to such data. This approach is similar in design to the Personal Health Train and would greatly expand the type of data which could be included within ODISSEI. Actual work is expected to start in early 2021.

Coordination Team Contact: Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

3.3.2 Automated Data Linkage

The program of work for Automated Data Linkage is currently being finalised and is being led by Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). Actual work is expected to start in early 2021 and will examine how the design of the ODISSEI Portal might be enhanced further.

Coordination Team Contact: Lucas van der Meer (lucas@odissei-data.nl)

3.3.3 The LISS Panel

The LISS panel, managed by CentERdata, consists of some 7,000 individuals from approximately 4,500 households. The panel is a representative sample of the adult population in the Netherlands.

In March 2020, ODISSEI launched the **LISS COVID-19 Grant** which provided researchers with time on the panel whilst the lockdown was in effect during the first wave of the pandemic. The call was exceptionally popular with 43 submissions, despite just 10 days between the announcement of the call and the deadline. Two proposals were granted and fielded in April and May of 2020. These projects are showcased on the ODISSEI website⁷ and generated considerable press attention.

In June 2020, ODISSEI launched the third round of the **LISS Grant**. The call for proposals closed on 30 September. 29 proposals were submitted. 4 proposals are COVID- related, the rest are general proposals. 40% of all submissions come from early career researchers (PhD Students and Postdocs), another 40% were submitted by Assistant Professors.

All proposals met the eligibility criteria and are now being assessed by the CentERdata for feasibility. Six researchers agreed to act as reviewers: Thijs Bol (UvA, sociology); Harry van Dalen (TiU/NIDI, economics); Jeroen van der Waal (EUR, political sociology); Yfke Ongena (RUG, methodology); Ellen Verbakel (RU, sociology, informal care); Anita Keller (RUG, occupational health psychology). The panel consists of 50% female researchers and all relevant disciplines are represented. Reviewers scores will be returned by the

⁷ <https://odissei-data.nl/en/2020/04/odissei-funds-corona-research-in-the-liss-panel/>

end of November and the decision announced by mid-December. The projects will commence from February 2021.

The COVID-19 and regular LISS Grants cost a combined **€ 95,000**.

In addition to the COVID-19 and regular LISS Grants, ODISSEI provided a **€ 555,000 subsidy to the LISS panel**. This budget has been used for the maintenance of the LISS panel in 2019-2020. Yearly fixed costs include personnel costs for panel management, subscription of broadband connection for panel members with initially no internet access, maintenance of hardware on loan to panel members, server and software license costs, and incentive costs for updating background variables and activation of 'sleeping' panel members (as to avoid attrition). Costs for the core study mainly consist of incentives for panel members, but also personnel costs for programming, testing, data cleaning and data dissemination. As a recognition to ODISSEI of the provided subsidy, CentERdata provided a 20% discount for using the LISS panel to projects from ODISSEI member organisations. Between July 2019 and June 2020, this amounted to a discount of € 120,566 across ODISSEI members.

Coordination Team Contact: [Kasia Karpinska \(kasia@odissei-data.nl\)](mailto:kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.4 The Hub

3.4.1 Community Management

As of 1 October 2020, Tom Emery moved from NIDI to EUR, where he will work full-time on ODISSEI. His tasks at ODISSEI will remain the same. The newsletter was sent out to 474 individuals in both Dutch and English. The number of subscribers has increased by 55% and 41% open and read the email, which is very high for a newsletter of this kind.

The community conference will be in a digital form on Tuesday 24 November, in the afternoon. The community managers are creating a program with a keynote session by Chantal Kemner, Mara A. Yerkes will explain how she used an ODISSEI LISS panel grant to study gender inequalities in times of the COVID-19 pandemic, and there will be a panel session on how several scholars see the future of ODISSEI.

Tom Emery and Lucas van der Meer conducted an ODISSEI roadshow online during the lockdown period to present the ODISSEI strategic vision to senior leaders at member organisations and they received significant feedback on the infrastructural needs of researchers and the member organisations. The two new community managers Suze Zijlstra and Eva Heitbrink are also conducting ODISSEI showcase events over the coming months to increase the visibility and engagement of ODISSEI amongst practicing researchers within member organisations. They will explain all aspects of using ODISSEI to researchers.

The communication costs were € 39,300 and € 133,520 was spent on staff costs.

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

3.4.2 Educational Programme

The educational programme is currently being developed and adapted to a virtual setting. In 2020, events including the Microdata Access showcase and the ODISSEI community day were cancelled or moved online which reduced the opportunities for effective educational engagement. In lieu, the new community managers are liaising with ODISSEI member organisations and graduate program officers to explore ways in which ODISSEI can foster greater coordination and fill perceived gaps in the educational resources and opportunities needed in order to conduct computational social science.

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

3.4.3 ODISSEI Social Data Analytics Team

The ODISSEI Social Data Analytics Team (OSDAT) was established in September 2020 and is already working on its first activity in association with a project on citizen science led by Peter Lugtig (Utrecht University). Currently the team is limited to Daniel Oberski (lead) and Erik-Jan van Kesteren. In 2021 the team will be expanded. The current work is focused on developing a procedure for identifying and prioritising social data analytics projects and defining the scope of the team.

Coordination Team Contact: Kasia Karpinska (kasia@odissei-data.nl)

3.4.4 Computational Social Science Grants

The program of work for the Computational Social Science Grants is currently being finalised in conjunction with the Netherlands eScience Center. The Netherlands eScience Center is currently running its annual general open call for research projects and it plans to use the Social Science proposals received in this call as a basis for shaping and developing a call for projects that is exclusively for ODISSEI member organisations in 2021.

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

3.4.5 Benchmarking

The program of work for Benchmarking activities is currently being finalized in conjunction with the Netherlands eScience Center. The Netherlands eScience Center will be developing benchmarking activities that help improve the application of advanced computational techniques to complex social science datasets such as detailed network or geospatial data in the OSSC. Such benchmarks will allow social scientists to rapidly establish best practices in methodologies that are relatively novel in the field of social sciences. Actual work is expected to commence in late 2021.

Coordination Team Contact: Suze Zijlstra (suze@odissei-data.nl)

4 Governance

ODISSEI now consists of **40 member organisations**. Almost all member organisations committed their financial contribution to ODISSEI until 2024, the end of the Roadmap project. A new participants agreement, formalising the distribution of responsibilities and ensuring the efficient functioning of ODISSEI, was sent to ODISSEI member organisations for signature on 16 October 2020.

The **Supervisory Board** now consists of Pieter Hooimeijer (DSW, chair), Carlo Schuengel (DSW), Henk van der Kolk (DSW), Arthur van Soest (DEB), Ruben Dood (Statistics Netherlands), Peter van der Laan (KNAW/NWO institutes and E-infrastructures), and Sander Steijn (public research institutes).

The **Management Board** has been expanded as part of the successful roadmap application and now consists of nine members: Pearl Dykstra (EUR, Chair and Director), Tom Emery (EUR, Deputy Director), Dorret Boomsma (VU), Tanja van der Lippe (UU), Marcel Das (CentERdata), Ruurd Schoonhoven (Statistics Netherlands), Annette Langedijk (SURF), Rob van Nieuwpoort (NLeSC), and Jacco van Ossenbruggen (VU). The Management Board now meets monthly to discuss and evaluate the program of work.

On 4 June 2019, Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) replaced NWO as host participant. EUR and an external fiscalist conducted a full assessment of ODISSEI's financial, legal, accounting and tax procedures and improved them where needed. **The Coordination Team** now consists of five individuals: Tom Emery (Observatory Manager), Lucas van der Meer (Operational Manager), Kasia Karpinska (Scientific Manager), Suze Zijlstra (Community Manager), and Eva Heitbrink (Community Manager).

As part of the Roadmap project, an **Advisory Board** has been established including Ron Dekker (CESSDA), Julia Lane (NYU), Melinda Mills (University of Oxford), Sally Wyatt (Maastricht University), and Amy O'Hara (Georgetown University). Due to travel restrictions the board has yet to meet but a virtual meeting will take place in early 2021.

5 Financial Results 2019-2020

ODISSEI aligned the reporting schedule of (a) the Task Leaders to the Management Board, (b) the Management Board to the Supervisory Board, and (c) ODISSEI to NWO. For this reason, the financial year now runs from 1 July to 30 June.

An overview of the financial results is given in Table 3.

ODISSEI is on a firm financial footing. In the financial year 2019-2020, 34 **member organisations**⁸ contributed a total of **€ 625,000**. Almost all have reaffirmed their commitment until 2024. As the interest to become a member organisation is still considerable, the Management Board expects an increase in contributions in the coming years.

In addition, 2019-2020 **NWO** has provided **€ 550,000** for ODISSEI's **core budget**. This contribution has been affirmed until the financial year 2021-2022, when it will cease to be given.

ODISSEI started the financial year with a **cash reserve** of **€ 647,000**, the result of an accumulation of underspending in the previous years. Underspending was unavoidable as long as ODISSEI was formally placed at NWO. ODISSEI did not have full access to its funds and any financial redistribution was subject to NWO subsidy guidelines. With the transfer to the EUR, ODISSEI has the required authority to set up and carry out its own calls for proposals. The Management Board followed the Council's (the predecessor of the current Supervisory Board) direction to invest the available cash reserve in digital infrastructure, and to have a negative result in 2019-2020 (**€ -204,520**). In comparison with 2018-2019, ODISSEI spent more on access grants, on the development of the OSSC and especially on programme coordination.

The cash reserve at the end of the financial year is **€ 442,080**. This reserve will partly (€ 362,000) be spent on the Roadmap project.

⁸ A further six new organisations joined ODISSEI on 1 July 2020 and will contribute for the 2020-2021 financial year.

Table 3 - Income and Expenditure 2016-2017 to 2019-2020

	(in k€)	2016- 2017	2017- 2018	2018- 2019	2019- 2020
Income		525	1,040	1,599	1,175
NWO contribution		400	550	550	550
NWO Bridge grant		-	-	499	-
Member organisations		125	490	550	625
Expenses		287	852	1,378	1,380
Data Facility		-	35	603	476
1.1 Microdata		-	35	278	297
<i>Microdata Access Discount</i>		-	35	278	257
<i>Microdata Access Grant</i>		-	-	-	40
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		-	-	325	96
1.4 Portal		-	-	-	83
Observatory		280	799	30	81
2.1 Data collection		280	799	30	81
<i>ESS National Coordinator</i>		-	-	-	45
<i>EVS Fieldwork</i>		-	160	-	-
<i>NKO Fieldwork</i>		-	170	-	-
<i>SHARE fieldwork</i>		280	439	-	-
<i>LIS contribution</i>		-	30	30	36
Laboratory		-	-	640	650
3.3 Survey innovations		-	-	640	650
<i>LISS panel</i>		-	-	548	555
<i>LISS grants</i>		-	-	92	95
Hub		7	18	105	172
4.1 Community management		7	18	105	172
<i>Communication</i>		7	18	23	39
<i>Staff</i>		-	-	83	133
Result (income minus expenses)		238	188	221	-205
Cash reserve (accumulated result)		238	426	647	442

6 Plans for 2020-2024

In the financial years 2020-2021 through 2023-2024, ODISSEI will execute the Roadmap project with the budget as earlier approved by the Supervisory Board and NWO. An overview is given in Table 4.

The NWO Roadmap grant is **€ 9,300,000**. The other funding streams are earlier, yet unspent, NWO grants (**€ 1,100,000** to finance ERIC commitments), member contributions (**€ 3,180,000**) and ODISSEI's own cash reserve (**€ 362,000**). This adds up to the budget for the entire project of **€ 13,942,000**, which will be spent more or less evenly over the four financial years.

Table 4 - Proposed Budget 2020-2024

	(in k€)	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	2023-2024	Total Roadmap
Data Facility		1,156	1,382	857	1,426	4,821
1.1 Microdata		394	444	350	700	1,888
1.2 Data products		-	-	-	-	-
1.3 ODISSEI Secure Supercomputer		601	638	246	333	1,819
1.4 Portal		161	300	261	393	1,114
Observatory		793	1,147	1,007	608	3,554
2.1 Data collection		590	941	759	522	2,813
2.2 Media Content Analysis Lab		60	62	63	86	270
2.3 Historical Sample of the Netherlands		71	72	92	-	236
2.4 Netherlands Twin Register		71	72	92	-	236
Laboratory		565	377	594	841	2,377
3.1 Distributed learning		71	84	-	-	155
3.2 Automatic linking		71	72	74	101	318
3.3 Survey innovations		270	220	520	740	1,750
3.4 Mass experiments		77	-	-	-	77
3.5 Citizen science		77	-	-	-	77
Hub		533	756	917	984	3,190
4.1 Community management		206	355	349	703	1,612
4.2 Education		5	35	36	80	156
4.3 ODISSEI Social Analytics Team		142	216	232	201	791
4.4 eScience grants		100	150	300	-	550
4.5 Benchmarking platform		80	-	-	-	80
		6,094	7,323	6,750	7,717	13,942

Annex 1 – Microdata Access Discount

Table 5 - Microdata Access Discount Projects (July 2019 - June 2020)

Applicant or Administrator ⁹	Affiliation	Project Title
Adriaan Kalwij	UU-REBO	Survival probabilities and retirement
Alexandros Dimitropoulos	PBL	Evaluatie en voorspelling autokeuze- en mobiliteitsgedrag
Anet Weterings	PBL	De concurrentiepositie van regio's en regionale arbeidsmobiliteit
Anja Dirkwager	NSCR	Zorggebruik en gezondheidsproblemen gedetineerden voor en na detentie
Anne-Fleur Roos	EUR-ESHM	Prestaties Nederlandse ziekenhuizen
Annemarie Gielen	EUR-ESE	Spill-over effects of government policies
Annemiek Vial	UvA-FMG	De predictieve validiteit van de ARIJ-Risicotaxatie
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Innovatie en innovatiepolitiek
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Impact of vitality and job tasks on retirement
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	the influence of workers skills and ict investment on firm's innovative performance
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Embodied technical change: Implications for sustainability
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Publicatie bestand EBB 2002
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Open innovation, networks, and firm performance
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Jongeren Not in Employment, Education or Training (NEET) gedurende de school-naar-werk transitie in Nederland
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	De voorspellende waarde van toetsen en schooladviezen op korte en lange termijn
Anouk Hölsgens	UM-SBE	Flexibiliteit van het Nederlands onderwijstelsel
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	School and study choice: Matching and return
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	Educational choices and health outcomes
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	Field experiment on audit rules with application to long-term care
Bas van der Klaauw	VU-SBE	Evaluatie loting scholen
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	The social returns to mental health care: Evidence from a Dutch payment reform
Bastian Ravesteijn	EUR-ESE	Human capital development in the Netherlands
Carla Haelermans	UM-SBE	Het effect van ouderbetrokkenheid via een app op huiswerkgedrag en leerprestaties
Casper Burik	VU-SBE	Genetic analysis of individual income and occupations
Chris van Klaveren	VU-FGB	Onderwijsstromen
Chris van Klaveren	VU-FGB	Onderwijsstromen
Chris van Klaveren	VU-FGB	Maatschappelijke positie mensen met een beperking in Nederland
Daniel Karpati	TiU-TISEM	Adverse health effects of financial distress: the moderating role of family firms
Diane Conforius	UvA-FMG	Arbeidsmarktpositie allochtonen ten zuiden Sahara
Dirk Brounen	TiU-TISEM	Energy efficiency in the housing market
Dorret Boomsma	VU-FGB	Heritability of twinning in the Netherlands
Edwin Slijkhuis	RUG-FGMW	De invloed van de school op de ontwikkeling van burgerschapscompetenties
Eric Smit	RIVM	Individuele effect van het bivalente HPV vaccin
Eric Smit	RIVM	ELIMS
Eric Smit	RIVM	Healthy districts: Gezondheidseffecten van de wijkenaanpak

⁹ For MAD applications, the named individual is often the data manager and not the researcher

Erwin Zijleman	CPB	De invloed van sociale zekerheidsbijdragen en belastingen op lonen en participatie
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Aanpassingen arbeidsmarkt
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Kansrijk onderwijsbeleid
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Indicaties en gebruik van langdurige zorg
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Structurele veranderingen op de arbeidsmarkt
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Huizenprijzen en werkloosheidsduur
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Woonoorden van Molukkers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Reikwijdte van agglomeratie-effecten in Nederland
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Evaluatie scholingsaftrek
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	De economische impact van huizenprijsschokken op zelfstandige ondernemers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Vermogens en schulden van Nederlandse huishoudens
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Financiële regelingen en arbeidsmarktgedrag
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Experimenten voortijdig schoolverlaten
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Decompositie consumptie
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Koplopers en volgers
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Bunching analyse huurtoeslag
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Gemeentelijk Sociaal Domein
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Substitutie in de ouderenzorg
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Financiële routes
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Vernieuwing eigen risico model
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Voorstudie effectmeting inburgering
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Financieringsvraagstukken bedrijfsleven
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Ongelijkheid
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Comparative advantage In the Netherlands
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Regionale verschillen in onderwijsuitkomsten
Erwin Zijleman	CPB	Buitenlandse vermogens en de inkeerregeling
Eva Jaspers	UU-FSW	De rol van sociaal kapitaal in de arbeidsmarktongelijkheid tussen mensen met- en zonder migratieachtergrond
Evert Meijers	TUD-ABE	MultipliCity
Frank van Dongen	PBL	de financiële haalbaarheid van binnenstedelijk bouwen
Gülbike Mirzaoglu	TiU-TISEM	The effect and prevalence of crime prevention measures: shutter adoption in the Netherlands
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Pendelafstanden
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Economic consequences of migration
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	The attractors of Dutch cities
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Urban consumers
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Regionale en stedelijke economische ontwikkeling
Hadewijch van Delft	VU-SBE	Housing prices
Hans Uytenhout	NIDI	Hongerwinter-project
Hans van Kippersluis	EUR-ESE	Income, health, and work across the life cycle II
Hendrik Letterie	VU-SBE	Hervormingen in de Nederlandse markt voor de langdurige zorg: De waarde van meer keuze schatten
Ilse Badenbroek	Nivel	Integrate Onderzoek
Jannes ten Berge	UU-FSW	The effect of automation on workers
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Sociale Staat van Nederland 2017

Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Cohortstudie statushouders
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Overall monitor sociaal domein
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Verdeelmodel jeugdzorg
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Verdiepende studie integratie
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Eindevaluatie Participatiewet
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Armoede in kaart 2018
Jannine Van de Maat	SCP	Engelstalig HO
Jannine van de Maat	SCP	Ervaren discriminatie 2019
Jannine van de Maat	SCP	Kansrijk armoede- en schuldenbeleid
Jeanne Gubbels	UvA-FMG	Langetermijneffect onderzoek interventies voor kindermishandeling en predictieve validiteit LIJ voor toekomstige zorgwekkende opgroei- en opvoedingssituaties.
Jose Carreno	TiU-TISEM	The effects of rising contractual flexibility on the dynamics of hiring practices, wages, and real outcomes.
Kars van Oosterhout	UM-SBE	Geographical accessibility and educational choices
Kevin Van Kats	UU-FSW	Overgang PO-VO: wie weet het beter, de docent of de Citotoets?
Lenneke Alink	UL-FSW	Nationale Prevalentiestudie Mishandeling van kinderen en huiselijk geweld (NPM2017)
Leoniek Wijngaards-de Meij	UU-FSW	Diversiteit, aanmeldproces en studiesucces van studenten UU
Maarten Van Ham	TUD-ABE	Neighbourhood effects, neighbourhood change and segregation
Maarten Van Ham	TUD-ABE	StatusCities: Migrant legal STATUS diversity and diversity dynamics in CITIES
Maja Djundeva	EUR-ESSB	Leeftijdsegregatie in Nederland
Majogé van Vliet	VU-FSW	Veranderingen in functioneren na zorg bij ouderen in Nederland
Marco Helbich	UU-GEO	NEEDS
Mariska Oosterveld	Nivel	Meer inzicht in (kwaliteit van) palliatieve zorg
Martijn Hendriks	EUR-ESE	De invloed van asielzoekerscentra op het geluk van omwonenden
Martijn Hendriks	EUR-ESE	Werk en geluk
Martijn Meeter	VU-FGB	De betekenis van becijferen bij examens in het VO
Martijn Smit	VU-SBE	Knowledge spillovers, absorptive capacity and the Dutch CIS
Martin Olsthoorn	SCP	Een beter bestaan
Michal Onderco	EUR-ESSB	No more tulips in Moscow? How Dutch companies respond to sanctions on Russia
Mirjam Knol	RIVM	Non-specific effects of vaccination
Narly Dwarkasing	EUR-ESE	ECB policy and Dutch households
Nicoline van der Maas	RIVM	Direct measurement of Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV) healthcare burden in young children
Olivier Marie	EUR-ESE	The power of the Dutch pill
Pascal Achard	TiU-TISEM	The transitional dynamics of cultural integration
Pascal Beckers	RU-FMW	Entrepreneurial trajectories of young migrants in the Netherlands
Pascal Beckers	RU-FMW	The relation between mental health and labour market participation of Syrian refugees
Patricia Rowel	SCP	SSN
Patricia Rowel	SCP	Effecten corona arbeidsmarkt
Pieter Bakx	EUR-ESHM	Financial and health risks: Household decisions and government interventions
Pim Kastelein	UvA-FEB	Pension funding, housing wealth and macroeconomic demand
Puikang Chang	UvA-FMG	Ruimtelijke en sociale dynamiek en buurteffecten
Raymond Montizaan	UM-SBE	Het causale effect van een geneeskundeopleiding op psychische gezondheid

Renata Rabovic	TiU-TISEM	Teacher discretion in tracking assessments
Ron Diris	UM-SBE	De invloed van omgevingsfactoren en uitkomsten in primair en voortgezet onderwijs op de latere uitkomsten van leerlingen in Limburg
Ruben van Gaalen	UvA-FMG	Sociale ongelijkheid om veranderingen in levenslopen
Sabien Dobbelaere	VU-SBE	Interaction between innovation and firm dynamics
Sabine Gans	CBS	Nationaal Cohortonderzoek Onderwijs
Sander Steijn	SCP	Scheidslijnen voortgezet onderwijs
Sander Steijn	SCP	Cohortstudie statushouders
Sander Steijn	SCP	Gebruik en niet-gebruik voorzieningen sociaal domein
Sander Steijn	SCP	Differentiatie in het hoger onderwijs
Shuai Chen	EUR-ESE	Lagged duration dependent survival analysis on the same-sex partnership formation and dissolution
Sjoerd Van Bekkum	EUR-ESE	ECB collateral eligibility and bank risk-taking
Sofija Pajic	UvA-FEB	LeadHealth
Steve van de Weijer	NSCR	Effecten van individuele en intergenerationele levensgebeurtenissen op crimineel gedrag
Susan Hahné	RIVM	Infectieziekten Kengetallen Ziekenhuizen (DHD)
Sytske Wieggersma	Nivel	Harmonization and integrative analysis of regional, national, and international cohorts on primary Sjogren's Syndrome
Tessa Jansen	Nivel	Telephone triage and follow-up in out-of-hours primary care: comparing trajectories for patients with high and low socioeconomic status
Thijs Bol	UvA-FMG	Organisations, occupation, and inequality
Tim Huijts	UM-SBE	Kinderen van PIAAC-respondenten
Tirza van der Straaten	UL-FSW	Schoolprestaties van dove en slechthorende kinderen in Nederland
Tom Van der Meer	UvA-FMG	Sociale zekerheid & politiek vertrouwen: een causaal verband?
Twan Huijmsmans	UvA-FMG	The urban-rural divide in political attitudes
Willemijn Bezemer	EUR-ESSB	Op zoek naar vertrouwen: begrijpen en verbeteren van jeugd/politie interacties in hedendaagse 'superdiverse' samenlevingen.
Wim Bernasco	NSCR	Broken homes and crime
Zhiyong Wang	UU-GEO	Vitality data center
Zoltan Lippenyi	RUG-FGMW	Embedded transitions: Critical changes in individual and organizational lives and equity in society
Zsolt Csáfordi	EUR-ESE	Skill relatedness in cities and firms